

Funding Startups: Between Growth and Risk of Failure – The Case of JUMIA

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ABSTRACT

This article explores the impact of financing strategies on the growth and bankruptcy risks of startups, illustrated by the case of Jumia, a pioneering e-commerce platform in Africa. Founded in 2012, Jumia quickly raised significant funding and went public on the New York Stock Exchange, thereby becoming the first African e-commerce company to achieve this milestone. However, despite its initial success, the company faced allegations of fraud, profitability challenges, and an unstable economic environment. Through an analysis of Jumia's financial reports and significant events in its history, this article highlights the complexities of financing African startups and draws lessons for other companies operating in similar contexts. The conclusions emphasize the need to rethink funding models to support a sustainable entrepreneurial ecosystem in Africa.

Key-words: *Startup financing, Jumia, E-commerce, Failure risks, Economic growth, Africa.*

RESUME

Cet article explore l'impact des stratégies de financement sur la croissance et les risques de faillite des startups, illustré par le cas de Jumia, une plateforme de commerce électronique pionnière en Afrique. Fondée en 2012, Jumia a rapidement levé des fonds importants et s'est introduite à la Bourse de New York, devenant ainsi la première société africaine de commerce électronique à franchir cette étape. Cependant, malgré son succès initial, l'entreprise a dû faire face à des allégations de fraude, à des problèmes de rentabilité et à un environnement économique instable. À travers une analyse des rapports financiers de Jumia et des événements marquants de son histoire, cet article met en lumière les complexités du financement des startups africaines et en tire des leçons pour d'autres entreprises opérant dans des contextes similaires. Les conclusions soulignent la nécessité de repenser les modèles de financement pour soutenir un écosystème entrepreneurial durable en Afrique.

Mots clés : *Financement de startups, Jumia, E-commerce, Risques d'échec, Croissance économique, Afrique.*

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research context:

Young companies, or startups, have become essential players in the contemporary economy, especially in emerging markets. Their capacity to innovate, introduce new products and services, and create jobs makes them engines of economic growth. However, the success of these companies largely depends on their financing strategies. While these strategies can enable rapid expansion, they can also increase the risks of failure, particularly in volatile economic environments.

In many African countries, startups play a crucial role in economic diversification and job creation. They provide innovative solutions to local issues, address unmet needs, and contribute to the rise of the digital economy. However, these companies face unique challenges, including limited access to capital, inadequate infrastructure, and sometimes restrictive regulations. These factors make financing startups in Africa even more complex.

The financing of startups in Africa is a significant issue with multiple dimensions. On one hand, access to traditional funding sources, such as bank loans, is often restricted due to a lack of sufficient collateral and limited credit histories of entrepreneurs. On the other hand, venture capital investors are still relatively scarce on the continent, although their presence is increasing. Consequently, startups must navigate various funding sources, ranging from angel investors to crowdfunding platforms, while managing the risks associated with each option.¹

The objective of this article is to examine the influence of financing strategies on the growth and bankruptcy risks of startups, using Jumia as an example. The research question guiding this study is as follows: How do financing strategies influence the growth and failure risks of African startups? By analyzing Jumia's journey, we aim to understand how financial choices have impacted its development and what lessons can be drawn for other startups operating in similar contexts.

1.2 Structure of the Article

This article is structured into two main parts: the first part addresses the theoretical foundations related to the concept of financing strategies and their impact on the growth of startups, with a focus on Jumia's initial growth phase. The second part presents the results of an analysis conducted on Jumia's challenges, including its struggles and risks following its rapid expansion.

2. THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS

2.1. Conceptual framework of the research

Financing is essential for the survival and growth of startups, yet it poses significant challenges. This section examines key concepts related to startups and their financing, the available funding sources, the specific challenges faced by startups in Africa, as well as the findings of previous research on fundraising and initial public offerings in emerging markets.

A startup is a young, often innovative company aiming to develop a product or service within a rapidly expanding market. These companies are characterized by their potential for rapid growth and their pursuit of innovative solutions. Startups typically operate in uncertain environments and are often funded by external investors.

External financing refers to funds obtained from sources outside the company, such as venture capital investors, angel investors, or crowdfunding platforms. In contrast, internal financing involves using a

¹ Badran, M. F. (2021). Digital platforms in Africa: A case-study of Jumia Egypt's digital platform. *Telecommunications Policy*, 45(3), 102077. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.telpol.2020.102077>

company's own resources, such as founders' savings or reinvested profits. Each type of financing has its advantages and disadvantages, influencing the founders' ownership structure and control.

Financing strategies

Financial strategies are essential for organizations to effectively manage resources and achieve their objectives. These strategies are generally categorized into **internal** and **external** financing, each with distinct sources, advantages, and disadvantages.²

Internal Financing involves utilizing an organization's own resources to fund operations and growth. Common sources include retained earnings, asset monetization, and owner financing. This approach allows the organization to maintain full ownership and control without incurring debt obligations or interest payments. However, it is limited by the amount of available internal resources, which may restrict the scale of potential investments or expansions.

In contrast, External Financing entails sourcing funds from outside the organization. Key sources include equity investment, debt financing, and grants or subsidies. This method provides access to larger capital amounts, facilitating significant investments and potentially bringing in investors with valuable expertise and networks. However, it introduces repayment obligations, interest costs, and may dilute ownership and control.

When formulating a financial strategy, organizations should assess factors such as the cost of capital, financial flexibility, risk tolerance, and growth objectives. A balanced approach, often combining both internal and external financing sources, can provide the necessary capital while managing risks and preserving control.

- Venture Capital is a form of external financing where investors provide funds in exchange for equity in the company. This method is particularly valued by startups due to not only the financial support but also the expertise and networks provided by investors. However, it often leads to the dilution of founders' ownership and creates expectations for rapid growth.

- Crowdfunding enables startups to raise funds from a large number of people via online platforms. This method is increasingly popular because it allows testing the appeal of a product while collecting funds. However, success depends on the startup's ability to effectively communicate its value proposition and mobilize a supportive community.

- Self-Financing or Bootstrapping is a strategy in which founders use their own resources to fund the company. This approach allows founders to retain full control over the business, but it may limit the ability to grow quickly. Many successful startups have adopted this model, demonstrating that heavy reliance on external financing is not always necessary.

² <https://www.ft.com/content/0d93cc76-4b1f-4c83-afdf-c940f180db08>

Figure 1: the challenges of bootstrapping³

Bootstrapping Challenges of Bootstrapping in Startups

Source : Fastercapital

Research indicates that the success of startups in emerging markets often hinges on their ability to secure funding and pursue initial public offerings (IPOs). For instance, a study analyzing IPOs from emerging market issuers between 1991 and 2001 found that these companies raised significant capital by listing on U.S. stock exchanges, suggesting that access to international capital markets can be pivotal for their growth and success.⁴ However, it's a misconception to assume that a startup's success solely depends on raising external capital. Many startups have thrived by adopting a bootstrapping approach, relying on personal funds, revenue generation, and efficient resource management. This strategy allows founders to maintain control and focus on sustainable growth. For example, companies like Mailchimp and Basecamp have achieved substantial success without external funding, demonstrating that bootstrapping can be a viable path to profitability and longevity.⁵ These insights highlight the importance for startups to clearly articulate their value proposition, attracting investors who prioritize long-term profitability over immediate returns. By focusing on sustainable business models and effective resource utilization, startups can position themselves for success, whether they choose to seek external funding or pursue a bootstrapped approach.

Funding for startups remains a major challenge, particularly in regions like Africa where access to capital is limited. Venture capital firms have become more selective, and the quality of startups receiving funding has declined, according to several observers. This situation is exacerbated by the fact that investors' exit strategies are often incompatible with the long-term needs of startups. It is, therefore, essential to rethink financing models to create a more sustainable ecosystem that is less dependent on traditional investment

2.2. Presentation of Jumia: History and Business Model of Jumia

Jumia was founded in 2012 by Sacha Poignonnec and Jérémy Hodara, with the ambition of becoming the leading e-commerce platform in Africa. In its early days, the company focused on creating a platform that allowed African consumers to access a wide range of products, including electronics, clothing, and everyday consumer goods. Jumia quickly expanded its operations into over 10 African countries, including Nigeria, Egypt, and Kenya.

³ <https://fastercapital.com/topics/challenges-of-bootstrapping.html>

⁴ Bruner, R., Chaplinsky, S., & Ramchand, L. (2006). Coming to America: IPOs from emerging market issuers. *Emerging Markets Review*, 7(3), 191-212.

⁵ <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/investing/082814/companies-succeeded-bootstrapping.asp>

Jumia's business model is based on connecting sellers and buyers through its digital platform, while offering logistical services to facilitate delivery. The company aimed to address logistical and distribution challenges across the African continent while democratizing access to a variety of products. By integrating payment solutions and forming partnerships with local companies, Jumia successfully established itself as a key player in African e-commerce.⁶

From its inception, Jumia received strong support from international investors. Its initial funding rounds focused on venture capital, with major players like Rocket Internet, a German investment firm, playing a crucial role in the company's early development. Other significant investors, such as MTN and Millicom, also contributed to its funding. These initial investments allowed Jumia to quickly expand its operations across multiple African countries, thereby strengthening its market position.

One of Jumia's significant milestones was its initial public offering (IPO) on the New York Stock Exchange (NYSE) in April 2019, making it the first African e-commerce company to go public in the United States. This operation allowed the company to raise approximately \$196 million, which was seen as a sign of confidence in the potential of the African e-commerce market. However, the IPO also created high expectations regarding profitability, a pressure the company is still struggling to manage.⁷

Despite its rapid expansion, Jumia faced several major obstacles. In 2019, allegations of fraud emerged when some investors claimed that the company had overstated its sales and customer figures in its IPO filing. These allegations had a significant impact on Jumia's image, leading to a drop in its stock price and raising doubts about its governance.

The company has also struggled to achieve profitability due to several factors, including high logistics costs in Africa, lack of distribution infrastructure, and increased competition. Financial scandals, as well as structural challenges within African markets, have contributed to slowing its growth. Despite these difficulties, Jumia continues to reposition itself by adjusting its business model to better address the realities of the African market, notably by focusing on fintech services and delivery.⁸

A study conducted on Jumia.ma revealed that 67.2% of respondents reported using e-commerce less than 5 times for their online purchases, while 24.6% stated they had used it between 5 and 10 times, and only 8.2% indicated they had used it more than 10 times.⁹

3. METHODOLOGY :

3.1. Methodology deployed:

Qualitative analysis allows for an in-depth exploration of the financing dynamics of African startups, with a focus on the experiences and perceptions of key stakeholders. This approach is particularly relevant for understanding the challenges and opportunities Jumia has encountered throughout its journey. Based on qualitative data, the study aims to uncover nuances that often escape quantitative analyses. This study is based on a document analysis, including Jumia's financial reports since its founding in 2012, as

⁶ MALLEK, C., & AZOUAOU, L. E. (2023). L'impact de la stratégie inbound marketing sur le comportement d'achat des consommateurs de JUMIA (Doctoral dissertation).

⁷ <https://www.bloomberg.com/news/videos/2019-04-12/jumia-jumps-on-nyse-debut-as-africa-s-amazon-goes-public-video>

⁸ Soumia, A., & Amel, G. (2019). L'analyse et l'évaluation des sites marchands: Cas de jumia. dz et Batolis. *Revue Organisation & Travail*, 8(1).]

⁹ EL HARAOU, ILHAM, & QMICHCHOU, M. (2018). La confiance du consommateur dans le e-commerce: cas de JUMIA. *Revue Marocaine de recherche en management et marketing*, 10(2), 224-237.

well as its **IPO** on the **NYSE** in 2019. Press articles and case studies are also used to delve into financial challenges, such as allegations of fraud and profitability issues.¹⁰

Finally, a comparative analysis of Jumia's financing strategies relative to other African startups was conducted. This analysis allows for the identification of common trends and significant differences in financing approaches. By examining various cases, the study aims to draw lessons on what works and what does not in the African context.

3.2. Presentation and discussion of results :

3.2.1 Presentation the Troubled Fate of Jumia: From Rise to Fall:

In 2016, Jumia achieved what was considered miraculous by becoming the first African startup to reach a valuation of one billion dollars. A billion dollars was an extraordinary figure at the time, and what made it even more remarkable was that this company conducted all its operations in Africa, in a new and emerging sector on the continent: e-commerce. This was only the beginning, as just three years later, in April 2019, Jumia would achieve another feat by becoming the first African startup to go public in New York.

During the first three trading sessions, its stock tripled in value. At the time, investors saw Jumia as a brilliant company that had successfully entered a market where none of the global e-commerce giants, such as Amazon, AliExpress, or eBay, had managed to establish a foothold.

Figure 2: The history of the movement¹¹

Source : Zonebourse

None of these companies had managed to establish a presence in the African market, a region filled with challenges and obstacles. Then, the COVID-19 pandemic amplified the appeal of online shopping, allowing Jumia to reach the highest value in its history, at \$62.43 per share, with a total valuation of \$4.3 billion.

¹⁰ <https://blog.jumia.com.ng/jumia-goes-public-on-the-new-york-stock-exchange/>

¹¹ <https://www.zonebourse.com/cours/action/JUMIA-TECHNOLOGIES-AG-57025225/graphiques/>

Figure 3: The growth period

Source : Google Finance

However, unexpectedly, while everyone anticipated a strong consolidation of the company and its competition with global e-commerce giants, the most drastic decline of the business occurred. A free fall that no one could foresee. Imagine that Jumia's market capitalization has fallen by more than ten times since 2021, with the stock that was valued at \$62 in February of that year now worth only \$3.

Figure 4: The period of decline

Source : Google Finance

The company, which just three years ago was perceived as irresistible and capable of conquering Africa and the world, is now on the brink of bankruptcy. So, why did this happen to Jumia? How did it reach such heights, only to fall so rapidly and without warning? The story of Jumia is, in fact, a tale full of contradictions.

In 2012, two French friends, Sacha Poignon and Jeremy Hodara, who were living in Nigeria at the time due to their work at McKinsey & Company, began to consider how to start a new and extraordinary project—one that, if successful, would change the world and be worth millions of dollars. McKinsey is one of the largest management consulting firms in the world, serving the biggest companies and governments, and developing business strategies. Thanks to their experience at McKinsey, these young men knew they could take risks and start any project, as long as they found the right idea. At that time, all indicators showed an unprecedented development of e-commerce businesses in America, Europe, and Asia, with the emergence of giants like Amazon, Alibaba, and eBay.

These companies all succeeded in crossing the borders of their countries and operating on a global scale, gaining significant popularity in Europe, Asia, and America. However, what connects them is that none of them managed to establish themselves and grow their business on the African continent. These companies viewed Africa as a source of numerous problems and obstacles, particularly due to the catastrophic logistics and transportation systems that complicated the delivery of products to customers. Furthermore, internet access in Africa was limited and expensive, and a large portion of the population didn't even know what the internet was at that time. Additionally, strict laws and political instability in many African countries added countless complications. All these obstacles led the previously mentioned companies to delay their entry into the African market, which they considered a future market to explore when the European, American, and Asian markets would be saturated.

The French friends, Sacha and Jeremy, realized that this was an ideal opportunity. At a time when large companies were struggling to enter the African market, they devised a strategy to succeed in this context, with the ultimate goal of selling their startup to one of the e-commerce giants for billions of dollars, ensuring them a comfortable life. However, these dreams are often easy and alluring, but on the ground, they encounter unforeseen problems and difficulties, which indeed happened with Jumia. In the early years of Jumia in Nigeria, and later in other African countries, the company faced many challenges. Every time it tried to find a solution to one problem, a hundred others emerged. The idea of buying a product online was unacceptable and rare among African populations at the time. Africa was just beginning to understand the internet. Even if a person accepted the idea of shopping online, it was nearly impossible for them to provide their credit card information for a remote payment, unless they had a bank account and a card.

Logistical challenges represented another complicated aspect for Jumia. In addition to poor road conditions, it had to face surprising situations, such as neighborhoods without names or house numbers. Some laws in certain countries also prohibited delivery by private companies. Thus, Jumia's priority in its early years was to create a system that provided solutions to these issues present in the African market. It was also crucial to start generating revenue from investors, as it was clear that succeeding in e-commerce in Africa would be a long marathon requiring a lot of money. The first thing Jumia established to overcome the distrust of Africans towards online shopping was cash on delivery, known as Cash on Delivery (COD). This allowed customers to order a product, receive it, and check it before proceeding to payment.

Additionally, studies conducted by Jumia on the African market revealed that distrust was not the only reason many people did not shop online; many simply did not know how to proceed. To address this, Jumia simplified the purchasing process on its site and added other services, such as the ability to buy via WhatsApp or contact an assistant who would guide them step by step until they finalized the purchase. Logistically, the company created its own logistics unit, named Jumia Logistik, and recruited delivery personnel with their own motorcycles and cars to reduce operating costs.

Amidst all this, Jumia was also striving to develop its strategies to attract new investors, most of whom were African partners interested in the African market. So far, everything seemed to be going well, or at least giving that impression to the public. However, internally, the situation was quite different. The name Jumia was beginning to establish itself in the African, and then global, market as a company that had created an unprecedented revolution in e-commerce in Africa. Year after year, Jumia was no longer seeking investors; they were the ones turning to Jumia to invest their funds. In 2016, the company's value reached one billion dollars, making it the first African startup in history to reach that figure. But, as previously mentioned, all was not what it seemed. In 2019, Jumia was to make a significant decision in its history: to go public in New York (NYSE), thus becoming the first African startup to do so. For a company that began in Nigeria and

whose majority of activities were concentrated in Africa, achieving this dream after just seven years of existence was an incredible and unprecedented accomplishment.

3.2.2 Results:

However, why do we say that this was the worst decision in the company's history? When any investor considers placing their money in a startup, they first conduct a process called due diligence, which involves checking whether the figures and results provided by the company are real or exaggerated. Jumia significantly exaggerated the results it announced to investors, concealing many persistent problems in the African market. The main issue was the return rate, which refers to the percentage of unsold products returned to the company. In reality, this rate was high, but Jumia had managed to hide it from investors. Anyone who has worked in the e-commerce sector in Morocco or Africa knows that this return rate problem is a reality in all African countries. Therefore, due diligence and verifying results and figures prove to be very difficult for investors. This is why many companies around the world raise hundreds of millions of dollars from investors, only to eventually go bankrupt, as these figures, results, and technologies used were nothing but lies.

But when you decide to enter the world's largest stock exchange and create such a buzz that all the media and global channels spotlight you, you must understand that it is not only investors who will conduct due diligence, but also all journalists, banks, and competitors seeking to find out if what you say is true or not. This is where Jumia made a fatal mistake. Jumia's entry into the New York Stock Exchange was very promising, and everyone thought the company would quickly integrate into the portfolios of the largest global investors. On the first day of trading, Jumia's stock price increased by over 75.6%, and the company's total market value exceeded \$3.9 billion.

What we are discussing now are very high and unrealistic figures, especially since the company operates in the African market, where everything is cheaper, from labor to advertising. Development costs are more than four times lower than those of some European or American startups. However, as mentioned earlier, Jumia's appearance on the stock market raised questions, and it was then that it received the fatal blow that would change its fate forever. In May 2019, Citron Research published a damning report attacking Jumia, claiming that the company had disseminated false and misleading information to convince investors to place their money. This report, produced by expert Andrew Left¹², stated that Jumia had intentionally deceived investors by providing incomplete information regarding the actual number of customers, particularly the return rate. The report also mentions the admissions of a former Jumia executive, who candidly stated that Jumia had exaggerated every figure regarding its success.¹³

Figure 7: Rapport of Citron Research

Source : Citron research

¹² <https://www.cnbc.com/2024/07/29/andrew-left-citron-capital-securities-fraud-los-angeles.html>

¹³ Citron Research. (2019). Jumia: The generational buy investors listen well. <https://citronresearch.com/jumia-report>

This report marked the first major blow to the company, leading to a gradual withdrawal of investors. Although Jumia was one of the biggest beneficiaries during the COVID-19 period, when people turned to online shopping and food delivery to avoid going out, this period only provided the company with a reprieve.

Figure 9 : Complete degrowth Corona¹⁴

Source : Google Finance

In other words, it only delayed its fall. Over the years, Jumia began to edge closer to insolvency. And because misfortunes never come alone, all the efforts Jumia made to energize the African market and encourage people to shop online allowed new competitors to enter this market, one by one.

Figure 10: Jumia's Decline: Paving the Way for Competitors in the African Market

Source : Zonebourse

¹⁴ <https://www.google.com/finance/quote/JMIA:NYSE>

In Morocco, for example, over the past two years, companies such as Temu, Marjan with Marjanemall, and Amazon have entered the e-commerce market, not to mention the giant Glovo, which forced Jumia to suspend its food delivery service, Jumia Food.

Jumia, often referred to as "the Amazon of Africa," has had a rollercoaster journey since its inception. As one of the continent's pioneering e-commerce platforms, the company has experienced significant growth, fueled by substantial external funding and innovative market strategies. However, this success has not been without its challenges. Jumia's story illustrates the complexities of operating in the dynamic yet demanding African market. From navigating the intricacies of venture capital to addressing allegations of fraud, logistical hurdles, and fierce competition, Jumia has faced numerous obstacles that have shaped its trajectory. This section explores the key issues that have influenced Jumia's growth and struggles, providing insights into the strategic decisions that continue to define its evolution.¹⁵

- **Fundraising: Advantages and Disadvantages of Venture Capital** Jumia benefited from significant fundraising, notably through venture capital investors like Rocket Internet and MTN. These funds allowed the company to grow rapidly and establish itself as a major player in e-commerce in Africa. However, venture capital has notable downsides. The dilution of founders' ownership and the pressure to achieve rapid growth targets can create tensions within the company. Additionally, reliance on external funding can create vulnerability, especially when investor expectations are not met.
- **Fraud and Governance: Impact of Fraud Allegations on Jumia's Reputation** Allegations of fraud have had a devastating impact on Jumia's reputation. In May 2019, a report by Citron Research revealed that the company had exaggerated its sales and customer figures, leading to a loss of trust among investors. This type of governance crisis can have long-term consequences on market perception and the company's ability to attract new investments. The decline in Jumia's market capitalization, which fell from \$4.3 billion to less than \$500 million, clearly illustrates the corrosive effects of such allegations.
- **Operational Challenges: Logistics, Infrastructure, and Competition** Jumia has also faced major operational challenges. The logistical infrastructure in Africa is often inadequate, with poor road conditions and inefficient delivery systems. These issues have been exacerbated by increasing competition from other e-commerce companies, such as Amazon and local startups like **Temu** and **Marjanemall**. The need to adapt to a competitive environment has pushed Jumia to rethink its operational strategy, but this has also highlighted the limitations of its initial business model.
- **Diversification Strategies: Repositioning Towards Fintech and Logistics** In light of these challenges, Jumia began to diversify by repositioning itself towards fintech and logistics services. This strategy aims to capitalize on the growth of the digital payments sector in Africa and to improve the efficiency of its logistical operations. However, this diversification requires significant investments and a deep understanding of local market needs. Emphasizing fintech could also help Jumia strengthen its value proposition and attract new customers

4. CONCLUSION

4.1. Summary:

The analysis of Jumia's journey as a pioneer of e-commerce in Africa highlights the complexities of startup financing in a rapidly evolving economic environment. Jumia experienced a meteoric rise thanks to significant fundraising, notably from venture capital investors like Rocket Internet and MTN. However, this

¹⁵ Peprah, A. A., Atarah, B. A., & Kumodzie-Dussey, M. K. (2024). Nonmarket strategy and legitimacy in institutionally voided environments: The case of Jumia, an African e-commerce giant. *International Business Review*, 33(2), 102169. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ibusrev.2023.102169>

rapid growth has been marred by fraud allegations that severely affected its reputation and ability to attract new investments.

The results show that operational challenges, particularly in logistics and infrastructure, also played a crucial role in the company's stagnation. The increasing competition in the African market has pushed Jumia to diversify its services by repositioning itself towards fintech and logistics. This diversification strategy, while essential for its survival, requires a deep understanding of market needs and significant investments.

In light of the results of this study, several recommendations can be made for African startups:

1. **Combine self-financing and external funding:** Startups should consider adopting a self-financing model, or bootstrapping, to maintain maximum control over their business. This would allow them to grow at their own pace, without external pressure to achieve rapid growth targets. At the same time, they should strategically seek external funding by selecting investors whose goals align with their long-term vision.
2. **Strengthen transparency and governance:** Startups must establish strong governance practices and be transparent in their operations. This includes clearly communicating financial results and challenges faced. Good governance can enhance investor trust and improve the company's reputation in the market.
3. **Invest in infrastructure and logistics:** Startups need to pay particular attention to the logistical challenges specific to their market. Investing in suitable logistics solutions can improve operational efficiency and reduce long-term costs. Creating partnerships with local companies to optimize the supply chain can also be beneficial.
4. **Adapt to market needs:** Startups must be flexible and ready to adjust their business model based on customer feedback and market developments. Continuous innovation and adaptation to local needs are essential for maintaining a competitive advantage.
5. **Proactively assess risks:** It is crucial for startups to conduct a thorough risk assessment before making major financial decisions. This includes implementing internal control mechanisms to monitor financial and operational performance.¹⁶

4.2 Opening

In conclusion, Jumia embodies both the opportunities and challenges faced by African startups. By adopting a balanced approach that combines self-financing and external funding while emphasizing transparency, logistics, and market adaptation, African startups can enhance their viability and growth potential. The lessons learned from Jumia's experience can serve as a guide for other entrepreneurs seeking to navigate the complex landscape of e-commerce in Africa.¹⁷

Thus, the future of Jumia remains uncertain, but it is also emblematic of the possibilities and obstacles that businesses face in Africa. Jumia also announced on October 16, 2024, that it will close its South African online fashion store, ZANDO, as well as its operations in Tunisia by the end of the year, as stated by its CEO, Francis Dufay. Amidst all this, one question lingers: will we one day wake up to the dreaded news of Jumia's bankruptcy after being the first African startup to reach a billion dollars and list on the New York Stock Exchange? Or will Jumia achieve a spectacular comeback and return to the market?

¹⁶ Peprah, A. A., Giachetti, C., Larsen, M. M., & Rajwani, T. S. (2022). How business models evolve in weak institutional environments: The case of Jumia, the Amazon.com of Africa. *Organization Science*, 33(1), 431-463.

<https://doi.org/10.1287/orsc.2022.1565>

¹⁷ <https://african.business/2019/06/economy/jumia-builds-powerful-brand-as-africas-first-unicorn/>

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